

Capabilities and Limitations of Museum Volunteers

Examples of Restoration Practice in Small Museums

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 Büro für
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Oettingen

Volunteer Museum Workers

Who are the players?

Capabilities

Examples

Limitations

Examples

Conclusion

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Volunteer
Museum Workers

What are the
possibilities?

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I would really like to join your organization as a volunteer...that is, on a voluntary basis...

Good! What do you have to offer us?

Volunteer Museum Workers

Who are the players?

- Social Clubs
(e.g. in [Spaichingen](#))
- Employees of a company
(e.g. the [BSW-Gruppen](#) of the Deutschen Bahn Co.)
- Active retirees
(e.g. [miners in Borken](#),
[textile workers in Bramsche](#))

Volunteer Museum Workers

Who are the players?

- Social Clubs
(e.g. in [Spaichingen](#))
- Employees of a Business
(e.g. the [BSW-Gruppe](#) and
Deutschen Bahn Company)
- Active Retirees
(e.g. [miners in Borken](#)
[textile workers in Braunschweig](#))

Spaichingen Social Club

– Club members with no previous knowledge

Moving a traction engine:

- Assistance with transportation
- Trained through seminars
- Simple conservation and cleaning jobs

Volunteer Museum Workers

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BSW* Social Club for the Preservation of Historical Railway Vehicles in Koblenz

– active, retired non-railway workers

- special skills “not required“
- “every pair of hands helps“
- close working relationship with the DB-Museum in Nürnberg
- Trained through seminars

*Railway Social Work Foundation (BSW)

Volunteer Museum Workers

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(e.g. [miners in B](#),
[textile workers in Bram](#))

Former miners of the
Preussen Elektra (E.ON)

– Skilled personnel with
no previous museum
training

from mining equipment to
museum exhibit :

- Planned training through
seminars
- Simple conservation and
cleaning tasks

Volunteer Museum Workers

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(e.g. in [Spaichingen](#))
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[textile workers in Bram](#))

Staff of a former clothing manufacturer

- Skilled personnel with museum experience since the 1990s

Previous museum work:

- Assistance with moving
- Simple conservation and cleaning tasks
- Technical maintenance and repairs of machines

Capabilities

Examples

- A Prussian T3- Locomotive in its Koblenz location
- The disassembly of a spinning works from the 19th century and its presentation in the Textile Museum in Bramsche

Capabilities

Examples

- The Prussian T3- Loco in its Koblenz location
- The disassembly of spinning works from 19th century and its presence at the Textile Museum in Bramsche

On the occasion of its 100th birthday, the T3 served as a playground locomotive in the Cologne Zoo.

In 1999 it was brought to Koblenz.

Capabilities

Examples

- The Prussian T3 in its Koblenz
- The disassembly spinning works from 19th century and its present the Textile Museum in Bramsche

The T3-Project 2001 - 2004

– Restoration goal:
“Condition of last use“

- Signs of long usage preserved / not operational!
- BSW-Group works according to the restoration plan of an outside expert
- Railway experts working together with restoration experts
- Mixed methods: Airbrush-retouching and low-pressure air abrasive blasting

Capabilities

Examples

- The Prussian T3- Locomotive in its Koblenz location
- The disassembly of a 19th century spinning work and its presentation at the Textile Museum in Bramsche

The Textile Museum in Bramsche accepted the „Willführ Woolspinning Mill" from Tangermünde/Sachsen-Anhalt into its collection in spring 2000.

The Willführ Wool Spinning Mill was fitted out with its requisite machinery from the period 1800 to 1860. The small business operated in the same location *unaltered* until 1988.

Capabilities

Examples

- The Prussian T3- Loco in its Koblenz location
- The disassembly of spinning works of the 19th century and its presentation at the Textile Museum in Bramsche

Restoration of a historical spinning mill. The Willführ Wool Spinning Mill at the Textile Museum in Bramsche

– Restoration goal between “in use“ and “laid up“

- Relocation from Tangermünde to Bramsche
- One-time start-up with filming!
- Textile technical experts in combination with restoration experts
- Restoration advice: Documentation, proposals for restoration goals and corresponding practices

Limitations

Example

- The Locomotive BoBo 50 in the Nordhessian Lignite Mining Museum in Borken
- Initially a volunteer treatment

Limitations

Example

- The Locomotive B...
the Nordhessian
Mining Museum
- Initially a vol

– Restoration goals not previously defined

Measures were left half-finished because:

- Large objects are beyond the volunteers' resources
- Goal and procedures were not defined in advance
- Necessary conservation measures were unknown

Limitations

Example

- The Locomotive B...
the Nordhessian ...
Mining Museum
- Initially a vol

– Restoration goal: “well cared-for condition of use“

- Planning and contracting of a restoration firm with more appropriate capacity
- Variety of surface treatments

Conclusion – volunteer work is applicable if:

- A full-time project manager is present in the Museum
- Financial problems exist
- Volunteer capability is rated appropriately – in advance!
- No pressing deadlines
- A restoration plan is in place

“Etiquette Manual” on the co-operation between employees and volunteers

Conclusion – volu

- Full-time project manager present in the Museum
- Financial problems exist
- Volunteer capacity is raised appropriately – in advance
- No deadlines ruling
- Restoration plan exists

“Etiquette Manual “ on the operation h and v

Co-operation will be more effective and pleasant for both sides if:

- Requirements and expectations are openly discussed
- Individuals agree to time-limitations for the project
- The experience of the volunteers is used and the work is related
- Both sides can learn from each other
- Within the agreed-upon framework, active and responsible work can be carried out independently
- The volunteer is informed about the entire project
- The work of the volunteers is mentioned in public relations
- The volume of work is in line with normal everyday life
- The volunteers can install a small, visible plaque to commemorate their work

(“Etiquette Manual“ by Susanne Meyer, Textile Museum, Bramsche)

